

1 **Assessment of radon risk areas in the Eastern Canary Islands using soil radon gas**
2 **concentration and gas permeability of soils.**

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14 To be submitted to Science of the Total Environment

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Abstract

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The Basic Safety Standard (BSS) Directive 2013/59/EURATOM of the European Union (EU) has stated the need for member states to establish national action plans to mitigate their general population's long-term risks of exposure to radon gas. Maps of radon-prone areas provide a useful tool for the development of such plans. This paper presents the maps of radon-prone areas in the Eastern Canary Islands (Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura and Lanzarote) obtained from assessment of Geogenic Radon Potential (GRP) distribution in the territory. GRP constitutes a magnitude that is contingent on both radon activity concentration and gas permeability of soils. An extensive campaign covering all geological formations of the Eastern Canary Islands was undertaken to locally sample these parameters. Geostatistical analysis of the spatial distribution of radon concentration in soils, permeability and GRP was performed on each of the islands, and the relationship between these magnitudes and the characteristic geological formations of the volcanic islands was investigated. Areas dominated by basic volcanic and plutonic rocks (originated by both recent and ancient volcanism) exhibit relatively low levels of radon in soils, and with the exception of specific cases of very high permeability, these areas are not classified as prone to radon risk according to international criteria. Areas in which intermediate or acidic volcanic and plutonic rocks predominate are characterised by greater radon activity concentration in soils, rendering them radon-prone. Given these results, Lanzarote is classified as an island with low radon risk all over its surface; Fuerteventura presents low-medium risk; and Gran Canaria contains extensive areas in the centre and north where the risk is medium or high. This classification is consistent with the risk maps obtained by National and European agencies from indoor radon measurements conducted on these islands.

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Keywords: Environmental radioactivity; Radon risk maps; Radon in soil; Soil gas permeability; Geogenic radon potential.

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49 **1. Introduction**

50 The environmental incidence of radon gas has been matter of study over the last decades due
51 to its adverse effects on human health. Elevated concentrations of indoor radon in homes and
52 workplaces represent a public health concern, as this gas is responsible for approximately
53 50% of natural radiation dose due to ionising radiations. The International Agency for
54 Research on Cancer (IARC) deems radon a Class 1 Human carcinogen due it being the
55 second most significant cause of lung cancer after tobacco (Elío et al., 2018). In order to
56 mitigate the negative impacts of the population's exposure to high levels of radon
57 concentration, the Basic Safety Standard (BSS) Directive 2013/59/EURATOM of the
58 European Union (EU) stated that "Member States shall establish a national action plan
59 addressing long-term risks from radon exposures in dwellings, buildings with public access
60 and workplaces for any source of radon ingress, whether from soil, building materials or
61 water". Such national action plans are supposed to include identification of radon-prone areas
62 across the entire territory.

63 Indoor radon levels represent a complicated function of several factors, such as the geology of
64 the area, building structure (for instance, building materials, presence and type of basement or
65 cellar below the house) and domestic lifestyles. Amongst these factors, the radon
66 concentration in the subsurface in the vicinity of the building, which is contingent on the
67 composition and types of rocks and soils, constitutes the main source of indoor radon (Nero,
68 2008), while building material is considered a secondary source (Cosma et al., 2013; Nazaroff
69 and Nero, 1988; Righi and Bruzzi, 2006; Szabó et al., 2013). Thus, in order to prevent the
70 radon hazard in a particular region, identification of those areas that (given the local
71 characteristics of the soils) may have the potential to generate high indoor radon levels is
72 essential. In general, radon-prone areas can be identified via two strategies: (a) direct
73 measurements of indoor radon concentration, or (b) in the absence of an adequate number of
74 high-quality indoor radon measurements, assessment of proxy indicators such as radon soil
75 gas concentration, terrestrial gamma dose rate or uranium/radium content in the soil and rocks
76 (Dubois and Bossew, 2006; García-Talavera et al., 2013). When designing a procedure to
77 determine the radon-prone areas, hybrid approaches tend to be developed, i.e., methodologies
78 that integrate all available information for several variables to create optimal tools that
79 facilitate the classification of the territory under study. For instance, in UK (Miles and
80 Appleton, 2005) and Belgium (Cinelli et al., 2011), radon risk maps have been obtained that

81 combine indoor radon measurements with geologic information, whereas in Germany
82 (Kemski et al., 2009) and the Czech Republic (Barnet et al., 2008) radon risk maps have been
83 obtained based on measurements of radon activity concentration and the gas permeability of
84 soils.

85 The main parameters that affect radon concentration in the soil and its transport towards the
86 external air comprise the concentration of radon precursors (which are dependent on the
87 nature of the geological substrate), the emanation coefficient (such as particle size, porosity,
88 water content and temperature), the transport process (advection and diffusion) and
89 exhalation. In practice, the direct measurement of radon exhalation towards indoor air appears
90 to represent one of the best indicators of the radon potential of the soil. However, direct
91 measurement of this parameter requires long time intervals, stimulating us to instead use the
92 activity concentration of radon in soil for this study.

93 In this context, soil gas permeability is a fundamental parameter for determination of radon
94 gas mobility (Neznal and Neznal, 2005). This parameter is contingent on porosity and terrain
95 grain size, and can increase with the presence of fractures, structural discontinuities or karst
96 phenomena. For equal quantities of emanated radon (radon moved from within the grain
97 towards the intergranular space or pores) in a terrain, radon flux can vary considerably with
98 permeability, and hence the radon concentration can vary as well. Permeability is significantly
99 conditioned by soil moisture (infiltrated in the pores), which at the same time depends on
100 different factors such as pluviometry and phreatic level variations. A rise in water content in
101 the soil generally stimulates an increase in the radon concentration, but as it approaches
102 saturation level, a sharp drop in measured levels of radon can be identified (Menetrez et al.,
103 1996) due to the abrupt reduction in soil gas permeability. The presence of a superficial soil
104 layer with low permeability can imply an increase in the accumulation of radon below (Johner
105 and Surbeck, 2001), and may also lead to a considerable decrease in the radon's soil-
106 atmosphere flux. This can occur owing to different causes, including the presence of asphalt,
107 water content close to the saturation level, or intrinsic causes of the material such as when the
108 soil contains clay (Wiegand, 2001). Other environmental factors such as barometric pressure
109 or humidity also exist, but due to their variability they cannot be included as indicators for the
110 determination of a terrain's radon potential.

111 The relationship between radon concentration in soil and indoors has been widely studied
112 (Appleton and Miles, 2010; Barnet and Pacherová, 2011; Barnet et al., 2010; Chen et al.,
113 2009; Kemski et al., 2005). The Geogenic Radon Potential (GRP) is a magnitude that is

114 dependent on both the radon activity concentration at a definite depth in the soil and the soil
115 gas permeability, and is defined as an indicator of the potential of the soil to constitute a
116 source of indoor radon (Neznal et al., 2004). This magnitude operates independently of the
117 influence of any factors related to buildings or living habits. In this paper we present the
118 results of several measurement campaigns of radon in the soil and its permeability, conducted
119 in the Eastern Canary Islands with the aim of obtaining the Geogenic Radon Potential map of
120 this Spanish province, this being a useful tool for the estimation of radon risk across the three
121 islands. This investigation's methodology could also be applied to territories with similar
122 geological characteristics, such as the Western Canary Islands, *Islas de Cabo Verde* or the
123 Hawaiian archipelago.

124 **2. Study area: Eastern Canary Islands**

125
126 The Canary Islands are a 500-km-long linear chain consisting of seven volcanic islands and
127 several minor islets (Fig. 1A). The archipelago has developed in a geodynamic setting
128 characterised by a Jurassic (circa 160-180 Ma) oceanic lithosphere at the African passive
129 continental margin. The archipelago developed over the past 30 million years as a result of the
130 west-to-east movement of the African plate over a mantle hotspot presently beneath the
131 western end of the archipelago (Carracedo et al., 2002). Three types of geological units can be
132 found across the islands (Carracedo et al., 2002): 1) basal complexes (or the pre-shield stage),
133 including turbiditic sediments belonging to oceanic crust intruded by sheeted dike swarms and
134 plutonic rocks of a broad compositional spectrum; 2) shield or juvenile volcanism; and 3)
135 post-shield or rejuvenated volcanism. From a geochemical perspective, the volcanic rocks of
136 the Canary Islands belong to the alkaline igneous series, typical of intraplate volcanism. This
137 igneous series is formed by a sequence of rocks whose composition evolves from ultrabasic
138 and basic terms (including volcanic rocks as foidites, basalts, basanites, trachybasalts,
139 tephrites, phono-tephrites and its plutonic equivalents) to intermediate and acid terms
140 (represented by tephra-phonolites, trachy-andesites, trachytes, phonolites, rhyolites and its
141 plutonic equivalents) The area of study is restricted to the eastern and older Canary Islands,
142 i.e. the islands of Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura and Lanzarote, the three islands are at present
143 day in their volcanic rejuvenated stage.

144 Gran Canaria (Fig. 1B) is a quasi-circular island with a diameter of about 45 km and an area
145 of 1,532 km². The highest point of the island is located in the centre at an altitude of 1,949 m.
146 From a geological point of view the island can be divided into two differentiated areas: the

147 southwestern or Paleocanaria and the northeastern or Neocanaria halves (e.g., Carracedo et
148 al., 2002; Guillou et al., 2004). The southwestern half (Paleocanaria) corresponds to the
149 island's oldest volcanism (ca. 14.5 - 8 Ma) belonging to its juvenile stage. This area includes
150 a broad compositional spectrum of both volcanic and plutonic rocks, ranging from ultrabasic
151 to intermediate and acid terms. In contrast, the northeastern half (Neocanaria) is mainly
152 covered by volcanic rocks belonging to the rejuvenated stage (ca. 5.3 Ma to actual) with a
153 more limited compositional spectrum, mainly dominated by basic volcanic terms (e.g.,
154 Guillou et al., 2004; Rodriguez-Gonzalez et al., 2009).

155 Fuerteventura (Fig. 1C) with an area of 1,660 km² is the second largest island of the
156 archipelago and the oldest one. The topography of Fuerteventura is characteristic of a post-
157 erosional island with Quaternary sedimentary deposits extensively covering the basal complex
158 (pre-Miocene) and the juvenile volcanism (ca. 21-12 Ma), with minor rejuvenated volcanism
159 (< 5 Ma) outcropping in the northern areas (e.g., Coello et al., 1992; Ancochea et al., 1996;
160 Carracedo et al., 2002). Most of the volcanic rocks, both juvenile and rejuvenated stages, are
161 basic in composition. In contrast, plutonic rocks belonging to the basal complex exhibit a
162 broad compositional spectrum, from ultrabasic and basic terms (different kinds of peridotites
163 and gabbros) to intermediate terms (syenites, foid syenites) and carbonatite dykes enriched in
164 REE elements (Mangas et al., 1997).

165 Lanzarote is the northernmost and easternmost island of the Canary archipelago, with a
166 surface of 846 km². Lanzarote, as Fuerteventura, present a flat morphology (maximum
167 elevation of 670 m asl) typical of a post-erosive island. After Fuerteventura is the second
168 oldest island, with juvenile stage ranging from 14.5 to 5.7 Ma. But, opposite to Fuerteventura,
169 rejuvenated volcanism (including historical eruptions) covers large areas of the island. Both,
170 juvenile and rejuvenated volcanism, are dominated by basic terms, with minor intermediate
171 volcanic rocks. Quaternary terrestrial and coastal sedimentary deposits are also present in
172 large areas (e.g., Coello et al., 1992; Carracedo & Rodriguez-Badiola, 1993; Carracedo et al.,
173 2002).

174 In order to analyse the relationship between the geology and concentration of radon activity in
175 the soils, a simplified classification of the geological rocks outcropping in the Eastern Canary
176 Islands has been elaborated (Table 1).

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180 3. Material and methods

181 3.1 Sampling points

182 Several campaigns were conducted between 2012 and 2018 to perform a screening of both the
183 radon concentration in the soil and the soil gas permeability across the region. The selection
184 of the sampling points was conceived in order to cover all of the geological units of the
185 islands, as well as areas with differentiated behaviour of several radiological magnitudes such
186 as terrestrial gamma exposure rate or activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , as determined in a
187 previous work (Arnedo et al., 2017). Thus, 131 locations in Gran Canaria, 36 in Fuerteventura
188 and 35 in Lanzarote were sampled to obtain a statistically consistent distribution of Geogenic
189 Radon Potential representative of the islands. In Figs. 1B, 1C and 1D, the spatial distributions
190 of sampling points are shown. Thus, the island with the lowest density of measured points is
191 Fuerteventura, which together with Lanzarote presents a lower variability of radiometric data
192 than observed in Gran Canaria (Fig. 1B); moreover, due to their smooth orography, these
193 islands are much more easily characterised. In contrast, a higher number of points were
194 measured in Gran Canaria because it presents a very abrupt orography and far higher
195 variations in radon levels were found. Another factor that was considered when establishing
196 the number of sampling points was that Gran Canaria represents the most populous island,
197 containing approximately 77.3% of the population of the province in comparison with the
198 9.9% who live on Fuerteventura and 12.8% on Lanzarote, justifying its deeper study.

199 The climatic variability of the area of study was also taken into account. The Canary Islands
200 are located in the transition zone between areas of temperate and tropical climate,
201 characterised by low and erratic rainfall (300 mm), mostly in low-lying areas due to the
202 presence of the Azores anticyclone for most of the year. The northernmost parts of the islands
203 are exposed to constant humid trade winds, and rainfall here can reach 1000 mm. In the south,
204 rainfall is considerably lower, sunny days are numerous, and periods of rain mainly occur in
205 the late-autumn and winter. Measurements of radon activity concentration and permeability
206 were primarily undertaken in periods corresponding with low or no rainfall.

207

208 3.2 Sampling and measuring procedure of radon gas in the soil

209 In order to measure the radon gas concentration in the soil, a probe designed by Radon v.o.s.
210 was used. This probe represents a cylindrical, hollow probe, measuring 12 mm and 8 mm in
211 outer and inner diameter respectively and 1 m in length, and equipped with a free, sharpened
212 lower end (a lost tip) of 12 mm diameter. Following the procedure, the sharp tip is inserted
213 into the bottom of the probe, which is in turn nailed to the selected depth. Finally, the tip is

214 pushed down to create a hollow in the lower end of the probe, permitting the collection of
215 soil-gas samples, which are drawn up the tube towards the radon measurement equipment.
216 Given that the Canary Islands have poorly developed soils, a sampling depth of 50 cm was
217 chosen. The soil around the probe was tamped to prevent the entry of fresh air when acquiring
218 samples.

219 The radon monitor used was the DurrIDGE RAD7, a silicon ion-implanted solid-state detector
220 that measures the concentration of ^{222}Rn by alpha spectrometry of the radon daughter ^{218}Po ,
221 which reaches equilibrium with its parent in about 15 minutes. It has a very low intrinsic
222 background (0.2 Bq/m^3) and an extremely low detection threshold, below 4 Bq/m^3 . In order to
223 measure the radon gas concentration in soils, RAD7 includes an automatic GRAB-sampling
224 protocol (DurrIDGE Radon Instrumentation, 2015). Soil gas is pumped for five minutes to the
225 internal chamber until the radon is uniformly mixed with air, and the sample is analysed
226 thereafter to find the radon concentration. While pumping, the air flow rate is about 0.7 L/min
227 and therefore 3.5 L of soil gas are extracted from the soil. If a soil porosity of 0.5 is assumed,
228 the sample will be drawn from a sphere of approximately 12 cm of radius around the
229 sampling point. Thus, the selected depth of 50 cm guarantees that there is no dilution with the
230 air from the surface. The counting time in the grab-sampling protocol is 30 min and the RAD7
231 has to be purged for about half an hour previously. Therefore, each measurement takes around
232 an hour.

233 The methodology for the determination of activity concentration of radon gas in soil was
234 successfully validated by participating in three different international comparison
235 measurement exercises of radon in soil gas. The first one took place during the International
236 Intercomparison Exercise on Natural Radiation Measurements under Field Conditions held at
237 the ENUSA facilities in Saelices el Chico (Spain) (Gutierrez-Villanueva, et al. 2012)
238 organized by the Environmental Radioactivity Laboratory of the University of Cantabria,
239 (LaRUC), and the state company ENUSA Industrias Avanzadas and financed by the Nuclear
240 Safety Council of Spain (CSN). The next two exercises took place at reference sites of Cetyne
241 and Buk in the Czech Republic in the framework of the Radon Intercomparison
242 Measurements at Radon Reference Sites (RIM) (Matolin, 2017) held on September 2014 and
243 September 2018 organized by radon v.o.s and the Charles University in Prague.

244

245 *3.3 Measurement procedure of soil gas permeability*

246 Parallel with the radon measurement campaign, we obtained the soil gas permeability at each
247 point using a permeameter RADON-JOK. The permeability measurements were carried out

248 almost simultaneously with the measurements of radon in the soil using the same hollow rod
249 hammered into the ground to a measured depth. The principle of the RADON-JOK equipment
250 consists of air withdrawal by means of negative pressure. The air is pumped from the soil
251 under constant pressure through a specially designed probe with a constant contact area
252 between the probe head and the soil. The constant active area is created in the head of the
253 probe by pushing the tip by means of the punch wire inside the probe a small distance. The
254 special rubber sack, via gravity and the help of one or two weights, pumps air from the soil
255 and facilitates measurements at very low pressures. The soil gas permeability is calculated
256 using the time spent by the rubber sack to be completely filled of air and employing a
257 nomograph provided by the company RADON v.o.s with the relationship between such time
258 and permeability. The RADON-JOK permeameter has a detection limit of 6 s that
259 corresponds to a permeability of $1.8 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$. The manufacturer's specifications indicate
260 that for very impermeable floors, with a time value above 1,200 s, a permeability of 5×10^{-14}
261 m^2 must be assigned.

262 **4. Results and discussion.**

263 **4.1. Radon gas activity concentration in soils**

264 *Gran Canaria*

265 Fig. 2 shows the histogram of the data distribution of radon activity concentration in the soil
266 measured in Gran Canaria, the corresponding statistical indicators and box plot.

267 As can be seen in Fig. 2, the distribution of data is asymmetric with a higher
268 frequency of low values, ranging from 0.5 to 150 kBq/m³. The distribution has a median of
269 8.8 kBq/m³, an arithmetic mean of 16.9 kBq/m³ and a standard deviation of 21.3 kBq/m³. The
270 box plot quantitatively shows that most values correspond to relatively low concentrations
271 (75% of the data are below 20 kBq/m³), with few values of high concentration (8% of data
272 above 50 kBq/m³). The kurtosis and asymmetry values (a.k.a. skewness) confirm that the data
273 follow a non-normal and non-symmetric distribution. The theoretical distribution that better
274 approximates to the experimental distribution is the log-normal distribution, attaining a
275 coefficient of determination R^2 of 0.9948. The Anderson-Darling test was applied, and the
276 result did not reject the null hypothesis at a 5% significance level, that the distribution of data
277 follows a log-normal distribution, with a p-value of 0.404. This theoretical distribution is
278 widely utilised in Geostatistics for the study of the spatial distribution of minerals and
279 formation of soils (Rendu, 1979).

280 Fig. 3A shows the map of radon activity concentration in the soil of Gran Canaria, computed
281 by ordinary kriging interpolation of the measured data. The empirical semivariogram used for
282 Krigging is shown in Fig. 3B. It shows a clear structure in which no relevant nugget effect
283 (intercept of the empirical semivariogram) can be identified. The empirical semivariogram
284 was fit to a theoretical exponential model, also shown in this Fig. 3B, from which it can be
285 inferred that the values are correlated up to a distance of approximately 5 km. This may be
286 considered the range over which geology tends to considerably vary.

287 This map partly reflects the geological structures explained in Section 2. Higher values of
288 radon in the soil were found in the centre and northeast of the island (the maximum with a
289 value of $150 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ is situated in the Tamadaba-Altavista Massif), approximately within the
290 limits of the zone named “Caldera de Tejada” (Tejada Basin) in Fig. 1B. The lithology
291 associated with these zones principally corresponds to materials from the first and second
292 magmatic cycle of the island (Ancient cycle and Roque Nublo cycle). A proportion of these
293 materials comprises plutonic rocks (such as dykes and plutons), volcanic magmatic rocks (for
294 instance ignimbrites) and differentiated magmatic rocks (trachytes, phonolites and syenites),
295 where radioactive trace elements such as uranium or thorium, elements from rare earths and
296 major minerals such as potassium are accumulated. Given that a higher concentration of radon
297 precursors can be found in the bedrock in these areas, radon activity concentration in the soils
298 was expected to be high, as was duly observed. Points with intermediate levels (between 30
299 and $50 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) were also found in the southern zone, in the extra-basin zone (corresponding
300 to rhyolitic structures of the Miocene edifice), and in the north, associated to post-Roque
301 Nublo volcanic cones.

302 The zones with low radon activity concentration in the soil are localised, as expected,
303 primarily in the northeastern and eastern parts of the island, corresponding to the most recent
304 volcanism (post-Roque Nublo), which as previously mentioned is characterised by the
305 preponderance of basic rocks. The zones of fluvial and aeolian deposits present very low
306 concentrations of both radon and natural radionuclides.

307

308 Fig. 4 shows the box plots of the data of radon activity concentration in the soil
309 corresponding to the various geological categories defined for Gran Canaria according to the
310 classification in Table 1. On each box, the central line indicates the median (second quartile or
311 Q_2), and the bottom and top edges of the box indicate the first and third quartiles (Q_1 and Q_3),

312 respectively. The ends of the whiskers represent the lowest datum within 1.5 IQR
313 (Interquartile range: Q_3-Q_1) of the lower quartile, and the highest datum within 1.5 IQR of the
314 upper quartile, and therefore not considered outliers. The outliers are plotted individually as
315 dots out of such an interval. Additionally, the point within the boxes represents the arithmetic
316 mean. The allocation of each sampling point to a geological code has been performed utilising
317 the digital geological maps provided by the cartography of SDI- GRAFCAN S.A. As can be
318 seen, the largest values are found to be associated to the geological codes 2 and 4,
319 corresponding to the soils in which intermediate and acid rocks predominate (volcanic and
320 plutonic). Given that 75% of the obtained values for codes 2 and 4 are below $20 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, the
321 arithmetic mean of the distribution ($25.2 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) is clearly affected by the extremal values
322 encountered, presenting a distribution with a very high degree of dispersion. Therefore, the
323 geometric mean, a better indicator in case of lognormal distributions, is considerably lower
324 ($13.4 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). Nevertheless, this value is considerably higher than the geometric means
325 corresponding to the geological codes 1 (ultrabasic and basic volcanic rock, $7.9 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), 5
326 (Sedimentary littoral deposits, $5.6 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and 6 (Sedimentary terrestrial deposits, 4.9
327 $\text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), as expected due to the geology of the different zones.

328 However, the complex geography of the island, its varied geological composition, the
329 intrusions of different types of rocks due to the island volcanic genesis and subsequent
330 rejuvenation cycles generally imply considerable local inhomogeneity, which accounts for the
331 fact that intermediate values (i.e. values between 20 and $60 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) appear to be associated
332 to points with geological codes 1 (basic rocks), 2 and 4 (acid rocks).

333 *Fuerteventura and Lanzarote*

334 Fuerteventura and Lanzarote are part of the same insular volcanic edifice (Carracedo, 2011;
335 Zazo et al., 2002) and exhibit similar geological characteristics, with low levels and little
336 variability of environmental radioactivity (Arnedo et al., 2017). Therefore, a less
337 comprehensive sampling was performed for these islands. The measurement campaigns took
338 place between the years 2012 and 2015, sampling a total of 71 points covering all geological
339 zones.

340 Fig. 5 shows the histogram of the distribution of radon activity concentration in the
341 soil, as well as the corresponding statistical indicators for Fuerteventura and Lanzarote. The
342 distribution of data for Fuerteventura ranges from 0.5 to $35.1 \text{ kBq}/\text{m}^3$, whereas for Lanzarote
343 it ranges from 0.1 to $12.1 \text{ kBq}/\text{m}^3$. Thus, Fuerteventura exhibits overall higher values than
344 Lanzarote, with medians of 6.3 and $2.9 \text{ kBq}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. In both cases these values are

345 considerably lower than those from Gran Canaria. Fuerteventura also presents higher
346 dispersion than Lanzarote, with a standard deviation of 8.5 kBq/m³ as opposed to 3.1 kBq/m³.
347 In this case, the theoretical distribution that approximates best to the experimental
348 distributions is again the log-normal distribution for Fuerteventura (attaining a coefficient of
349 determination R² of 0.7659) and the exponential distribution for Lanzarote (R²=0.8498),
350 assertions which were confirmed again by the test of Anderson-Darling.

351 Fig. 6 displays the map of radon activity concentration in the soil for Fuerteventura
352 and Lanzarote, computed by interpolation by means of the kriging method. For these islands,
353 the exponential model for the empirical semivariogram reaches the maximum variance (sill)
354 at approximately 10 km and 6.4 km, respectively. This fact confirms that both islands are
355 more homogeneous than Gran Canaria as far as radon in the soil is concerned.

356 Overall, the distribution of radon on Fuerteventura according to the soil map is congruent
357 with the geology of the island as explained in Section 2. Low values of radon activity
358 concentration in the soil are found across most of the island, which is dominated by igneous
359 basic rocks (such as basalts) and ultrabasic (including pyroxenites and peridotites) from the
360 basal complex and the subaerial volcanism unity (Miocene and recent volcanism). Two local
361 maxima are located in the basal complex in zones of differentiated rocks (especially syenites,
362 trachytes and carbonatites), in the massif of Betancuria and at the mountain of Tindaya
363 (trachy-rhyolites). A third local maximum was found outside the basal complex, located over
364 deposits (gravitational slides) of slopes in the ravine of Pozo Negro, and belonging to
365 subaerial volcanic edifices from the cycle of Miocene volcanism (central edifice) (Ancochea
366 et al., 1996), whose soils are principally conformed by basalts, as well as to a lesser extent by
367 series of differentiated formations, middle-alkaline and peralkaline-trachytes.

368 Lanzarote presents the lowest soil radon activity concentration and variability of the
369 islands studied. The values obtained accord with the geology of the island, in which 98% of
370 the rocks are basaltic, with very little presence of radioactive minerals (olivine and pyroxene),
371 there being no natural radionuclides in the volcanic glass. The maximum values are found in
372 the south of the island, in the vicinity of Montaña Roja, a 1.2 million-year-old volcano located
373 above the emerged part of the Miocene building of Los Ajaches (14 Ma) and largely
374 constituted of alkaline basalt and trachybasalt (Zazo, 2002), and related to the group of
375 volcanoes belonging to the quaternised fissural volcanism (group of volcanoes in the area of
376 Teguisse) (Carracedo and Rodríguez-Badiola, 1993). Suárez Mahou and Fernández Amigot

377 (1996) have suggested that a proportion of thorium of 0.1 ppm and 0.02 ppm of uranium can
378 be found in ultrabasic igneous rocks.

379 Fig. 7 shows the box plot of the data of radon activity concentration in the soil
380 corresponding to the various geological categories that exist on Fuerteventura and Lanzarote,
381 defined according to the classification in Table 1. Again, in Fuerteventura local maxima
382 correspond to codes 2 and 4. The uniformity of Lanzarote can be appreciated in Fig. 7B,
383 where only soils corresponding to codes 1 “Ultrabasic and basic rocks” and 5 “Sedimentary
384 littoral deposits” can be identified.

385 **4.2. Soil gas permeability.**

386 As previously mentioned, soil gas permeability is a fundamental parameter that can prove
387 decisive for the release of radon to the atmosphere or its accumulation in the soil
388 (Castelluccio et al., 2010). A greater degree of permeability permits the upward migration of
389 radon, facilitating its exhalation to the atmosphere, and consequently a smaller amount will
390 remain in the ground. In this work, the range of permeability values was divided into three
391 categories following the thresholds established by Neznal and Neznal (2005) on the basis of
392 their experience, as displayed in Table 2.

393 Fig. 8A uses box plots to summarise the distribution of soil gas permeability data
394 obtained for the three islands. It should be noted that the measurement campaigns of Gran
395 Canaria, Fuerteventura and Lanzarote were carried out in periods of very low rainfall in the
396 summer and autumn, in an effort to make the measurement conditions as homogeneous as
397 possible. As can be observed, the soils of the three islands are mostly located in the middle-
398 high permeability range. Gran Canaria presents 52% high-permeability soils, relative to
399 Fuerteventura with 39% and Lanzarote with only 35%. Only Gran Canaria and Fuerteventura
400 have low-permeability soils, with percentages of 18% and 25%, respectively. Again,
401 Lanzarote is the most homogeneous island as far as permeability is concerned, with 65% of its
402 soils exhibiting medium permeability.

403 Figs. 8B to 8D show the maps of soil gas permeability for the three islands. In Gran Canaria,
404 the soils with low permeability are mainly located in the central and northwestern zones,
405 corresponding to the most eroded environments on the island, which in many cases exhibits
406 very little soil. In the north and east of the island, soils with high permeability predominate. In
407 the southern zone of the island, the sampled soils have medium and high permeabilities.
408 However, regarding the interpretation of these results, it is necessary to be cautious, for it is

409 customary on the island of Gran Canaria to move soils from one area to another for crops.
410 Even though attempts were made to conduct measurements on lands unaltered by humans,
411 some densely populated areas exist in which the totality of measurements cannot be
412 guaranteed to have fulfilled such a condition. A significant proportion of the territory of
413 Fuerteventura corresponds to basalts, which exhibit a high level of permeability. Low-
414 permeability soils appear within the basal complex, corresponding to areas of heavily eroded
415 soils. The soils formed by sands and marine sediments have medium and high permeability.
416 Overall, and as mentioned above, in Lanzarote the soils have medium permeability, and as is
417 true of Fuerteventura, there are areas of high permeability associated with old basalts.

418 **4.3. Geogenic Radon Potential and radon-prone areas**

419 The Geogenic Radon Potential (GRP) is a magnitude defined as providing a quantitative
420 measurement regarding “what the earth delivers” in terms of radon (Bossew, 2015).
421 Nevertheless, a single definition of GRP does not exist, with diverse parameters used by
422 different authors and national regulators, such as in the Czech Republic (Neznal et al., 2004),
423 Germany (Kemski et al., 2001), France (Ielsch et al., 2010), Switzerland (Piller and Johner,
424 1998; Johner and Surbeck, 2001) and Sweden (Åkerblom, 1986). Nevertheless, most authors
425 define GRP in terms of a combination of radon activity concentration in soils and soil gas
426 permeability. In this work we adopt a heuristic approach similar to that proposed by Neznal et
427 al. (2004), defined through Eq. (1), where C_{Rn} is the radon activity concentration in the soil
428 (kBqm^{-3}) and k is the soil gas permeability (m^2).

429

$$430 \quad GRP = \left(\frac{C_{Rn}}{-\log_{10}(k) - 10} \right) \quad (1)$$

431 Maps of Geogenic Radon Potential represent useful tools to identify regions where there is a
432 higher probability of significant levels of indoor radon appearing due to natural sources, when
433 few or no previous indoor radon measurements are available. In addition, the GRP maps can
434 be used to prioritise those areas where it is deemed necessary to reinforce indoor radon
435 measurements as high levels of activity concentration in dwellings are expected.

436 According to the 2014 Basic Safety Standards (EU-BSS) for protection against ionising
437 radiation of the European Union, a Radon Prone Area (RPA) is defined as a geographical zone
438 or administrative region where the radon concentration (as an annual average) in a significant
439 number of buildings is expected to exceed the relevant national reference level. Even though
440 the BSS definition is based on indoor radon concentration, several regulators instead (or in

441 addition) opt to estimate it by means of other radon-related variables. One common approach
442 is to use a Radon Index based on the values of GRP to categorise the radon risk of a territory.
443 Based on numerous years of extensive research, in the Czech Republic three categories for
444 Radon Prone Areas depending on the values of the GRP has been established: R.I. Low
445 (GRP<10), R.I. Medium (10<GRP<35) and R.I. High (35<GRP).

446

447 Following the Czech classification, the soils of Fuerteventura and Lanzarote are characterised
448 on average (arithmetic) by low values of GRP, while the soils of Gran Canaria would be
449 characterised on average (arithmetic) by medium GRP. If the three islands were represented
450 by their geometric mean, it would lower the classification of Gran Canaria towards low GRP
451 as well. This fact was illustrated in Fig. 9, displaying the box plots of radon potential by
452 islands. The geometric means of the three distributions are in the low-risk zone, whereas the
453 high-risk points correspond to the high-value data of the islands of Gran Canaria and
454 Fuerteventura. For this reason, the arithmetic mean of the island of Gran Canaria is at medium
455 risk. It is also interesting to see how virtually the entire island of Lanzarote exists below the
456 low risk line.

457 Neznal et al. (2004) have proposed a graphic representation for GRP, as displayed in Fig.
458 10A. This diagram is a modification of that proposed by Barnet (1994). In this diagram, the
459 empirical criteria established by Neznal et al. (2004) are represented using straight lines in
460 order to delimit the low-medium and medium-high radon index (RI) zones. Following these
461 criteria on Gran Canaria, we found that 63.4% of the measured points are in the low RI
462 category, 36.6% belong to the medium RI category, and the remaining 10.7% in the high RI
463 category. This representation clearly explains the fact that points with the same concentration
464 of radon, but different levels of permeability can be associated with different levels of radon
465 risk. It can also be appreciated that for radon activity concentrations above 35-40 kBq m⁻³,
466 soils cannot be classified as low risk. Hence, this is an outstanding tool that facilitates
467 decision-making and permits exclusion of the possible presence of high levels of indoor radon
468 due to the surrounding soils and the geological environment of a house. In Fig. 10A the GRP
469 values were labelled by their simplified geological code. As can be seen, most of the points
470 located in the high-risk area of the diagram correspond to code 2 (Intermediate or Acidic
471 Volcanic Rocks), as had been expected given the geochemical characteristics of this substrate.
472 Some points belonging to basaltic soils (code 1) with fairly low values of radon in the soil are
473 also located in the high-risk area due to the fact that they are situated in zones of high
474 permeability.

475 These facts are reflected in Fig. 10B, where the map of GRP (in natural logarithmic scale) for
476 Gran Canaria is shown. This map can be used as an estimator of the Radon Prone Areas for
477 the island. A colour code of nine levels was adopted corresponding to three main categories of
478 R.I defined above. The low-medium and medium-high R.I limits are, respectively, 2.203 and
479 3.555, corresponding to the natural logarithm of the aforementioned R.I. limits (10 and 35).
480 This map shows that a substantial part of the surface of the island can be classified as low
481 radon risk. These areas mainly correspond to basaltic soils and are found in the periphery of
482 the island. The medium- and high-risk zones are located in the north-centre of the island,
483 where the presence of soils coming from intermediate or acidic volcanic rocks (trachytes -
484 phonolites) is more significant. These final zones cover parts of the municipalities of Arucas,
485 Firgas, Moya, Santa Brígida, Teror, San Mateo, Valleseco, Tejeda, Artenara, Agaete,
486 Valsequillo, San Bartolomé de Tirajana and Mogán, which contain approximately 125,000
487 inhabitants (15% of the total population of the island). Dwellings in these areas primarily
488 constitute traditional village single-family land houses and cave houses, buildings that are
489 more prone to the accumulation of indoor radon than the apartment buildings common in
490 large cities in Spain.

491 Fig. 11A displays the radon risk diagram for Fuerteventura, where all values except
492 one are concentrated in the area of low- or medium-low risk of radon. The only exception
493 observed in the area of high risk (although almost at the medium-high border) is mainly due
494 to the high permeability of the soil at that point, as the radon activity concentration is below
495 40 kBq/m^3 . Fig. 11B shows the RPA map for Fuerteventura. As expected according to its
496 geology, most of the island presents a low-radon risk profile, albeit slightly higher in zones of
497 the basal complex where some rocks from codes 2 and 4 outcrop. Regarding Lanzarote, Fig.
498 12A demonstrates that nearly all of the values are located in the low radon risk zone, with a
499 few points situated above the straight line delineating the transition between the low-risk and
500 medium-risk zones, not due to high radon concentrations, but to corresponding high-
501 permeability values. Accordingly, the map of RPA of Lanzarote shown in Fig. 12B presents
502 the only low-risk category throughout the territory.

503

504 **5. Summary and conclusions**

505 The use of a Risk Index based on the GRP for the zonal classification of the Eastern Canary
506 Islands permits classification of the islands of Lanzarote and Fuerteventura as being areas of

507 low radon risk, whereas Gran Canaria has a large area classified as being at potentially high
508 radon risk. The maps developed in this work may prove a highly useful tool for the authorities
509 responsible for the monitoring and control of radon exposure in the territory of the Canary
510 Islands, both when preparing action plans for sampling and preventing the appearance of
511 indoor radon in dwellings and workplaces. The Spanish Building Code is currently under
512 revision in order to include protection against radon by means of classifying the country and
513 building site in question under several radon risk categories, as well as the inclusion of radon-
514 resistant techniques in new buildings. The GPR maps based on soil properties are ideal for
515 this task and are already being used in several countries such as the Czech Republic and
516 Germany. The zonal classification obtained accords with the indoor radon risk map of the
517 Canary Islands included in the European Radon Map developed by the EU-JRC (Gruber et al.,
518 2013). This map has been developed from direct indoor measurements in houses, and
519 although it has poor resolution in the island territory, it coincides with the classification of
520 Lanzarote and Fuerteventura as non-prone areas and the centre of Gran Canaria as a radon-
521 prone area. This fact is also reflected in the map of radon potential in Spain developed by the
522 Nuclear Safety Council of Spain based on terrestrial gamma radiation, geology and indoor
523 radon data (García-Talavera et al., 2013; Sainz Fernández et al., 2017; Consejo de Seguridad
524 Nuclear, 2017)

525 It is important to note that the classification of a certain area as being at low risk of radon
526 does not mean that radon concentrations above the reference level of 300 Bq/m^3 will not
527 occur in any building; it simply means that this is unlikely. In the same way, a high-risk area
528 does not imply that any house built in the zone will necessarily exceed the established
529 reference level.

530

531 **Acknowledgements**

532 This work was financed by the Spanish Nuclear Safety Council through a grant of its R&D
533 programme 2012 for the project “Estudio de las concentraciones radón en viviendas lugares
534 de trabajo y materiales de construcción en las Islas Canarias Orientales”.

535 The authors are particularly grateful to F.J. Pérez-Torrado for his strong support in the
536 interpretation of the geology of the Canary Islands.

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Fig. 1. Geographic localisation of the Canary Islands (A). Simplified geological maps and sampling point distribution for Gran Canaria (B), Fuerteventura (C) and Lanzarote (D) (Extracted from Carracedo et al., 2002). The white circles correspond to the sampling points. All geological ages provided in Mega-annum (Ma).

Table 1. Simplified classification of the geological materials of the Eastern Canary Islands

Code 1.	<i>Ultrabasic to basic volcanic rocks</i> (foidites, basanites, basalts, tephrites, trachybasalts, phono-tephrites)
Code 2	<i>Intermediate to acid volcanic rocks</i> (tephra-phonolites, trachy-andesites, trachytes, phonolites, rhyolites)
Code 3	<i>Ultrabasic to basic plutonic and subvolcanic rocks</i> (peridotites, gabbros)
Code 4	<i>Intermediate to acid plutonic and subvolcanic rocks</i> (syenites, foid syenites) and carbonatite subvolcanic rocks
Code 5	<i>Sedimentary littoral deposits</i> (sand and gravel beaches and sand dunes)
Code 6	<i>Sedimentary terrestrial deposits</i> (clay, silt, sand and gravel alluvial and colluvial deposits, and soils)

Fig. 2. Histograms and box plot of the data distribution of radon activity concentration in the soil and statistical indicators for Gran Canaria.

724

Fig. 3. (A) Map of radon activity concentration in the soil at 50 cm depth (UTM coordinates are given in m) in Gran Canaria. (B) Corresponding semivariogram. Lag distance (h) is the distance that separates the location of two measuring points.

725

Fig. 4. Box plot of radon activity concentration in different geological formations of Gran Canaria.

726

Fig. 5. Histograms and box plot of radon activity concentration in the soil and statistical indicators for Fuerteventura (A) and Lanzarote (B).

727

Fig. 6. Maps of radon activity concentration in the soil at 50 cm depth in Fuerteventura (A) and Lanzarote (B) (UTM coordinates are given in m).

728

Fig. 7. Box plots of radon activity concentration on different geological formations of Fuerteventura (A) and Lanzarote (B). (UTM coordinates are given in m).

729

Table 2. Classification of the soil gas permeability (Neznal and Neznal, 2005).

Class	Permeability (m^2)
High	$k > 4.0 \cdot 10^{-12}$
Medium	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-12} m^2 \geq k \geq 4.0 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Low	$k < 4.0 \cdot 10^{-13}$

730

731

Fig. 8. (A) Box plots of soil gas permeability in the three islands. Maps of permeability of (B) Gran Canaria, (C) Fuerteventura, (D) Lanzarote.

732

Fig. 9. Box plot of Geogenic Radon Potential in Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura and Lanzarote.

733

Fig. 10. (A) Diagram of radon risk for Gran Canaria. (B) Map of Radon Prone Areas of Gran Canaria.

Fig. 11. (A) Diagram of radon risk for Fuerteventura. (B) Map of Radon Prone Areas of Fuerteventura.

Fig. 12. (A) Diagram of radon risk for Lanzarote. (B) Map of Radon Prone Areas of Lanzarote.

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Class	Permeability (m^2)
High	$k > 4.0 \cdot 10^{-12}$
Medium	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-12} m^2 \geq k \geq 4.0 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Low	$k < 4.0 \cdot 10^{-13}$

Fig. 1. Geographic localisation of the Canary Islands (A). Simplified geological maps and sampling point distribution for Gran Canaria. (B), Fuerteventura (C) and Lanzarote (D) (Extracted from Carracedo et al., 2002). The white circles correspond to the sampling points. All geological ages provided in Mega-annum (Ma).

Fig. 2. Histograms and box plot of the data distribution of radon activity concentration in the soil and statistical indicators for Gran Canaria.

Fig. 3. (A) Map of radon activity concentration in the soil at 50 cm depth (UTM coordinates are given in m) in Gran Canaria. (B) Corresponding semivariogram. Lag distance (h) is the distance that separates the location of two measuring points.

Fig. 4. Box plot of radon activity concentration in different geological formations of Gran Canaria.

Fig. 5. Histograms and box plot of radon activity concentration in the soil and statistical indicators for Fuerteventura (A) and Lanzarote (B).

Fig. 6. Maps of radon activity concentration in the soil at 50 cm depth in Fuerteventura (A) and Lanzarote (B) (UTM coordinates are given in m).

Fig. 7. Box plots of radon activity concentration on different geological formations of Fuerteventura (A) and Lanzarote (B). (UTM coordinates are given in m).

Fig. 8. (A) Box plots of soil gas permeability in the three islands. Maps of permeability of (B) Gran Canaria, (C) Fuerteventura, (D) Lanzarote.

Fig. 9. Box plot of Geogenic Radon Potential in Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura and Lanzarote.

Fig. 10. (A) Diagram of radon risk for Gran Canaria. (B) Map of Radon Prone Areas of Gran Canaria.

Fig. 11. (A) Diagram of radon risk for Fuerteventura. (B) Map of Radon Prone Areas of Fuerteventura.

Fig. 12. (A) Diagram of radon risk for Lanzarote. (B) Map of Radon Prone Areas of Lanzarote.